

Classroom Management, Motivation and Academic Performance: The Perspective of Students in Business English Classes at Ba Ria-Vung Tau University

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ABSTRACT: This study applied self-determination theory to understand the roles of teacher's behavioral control and care in student learning outcomes. The research explored the relationship between components of classroom management and academic performance via the mediating role of motivation to learn of students in Business English classes at Ba Ria - Vung Tau University. By applying qualitative research combined with quantitative research (mixed method), this research tested the relationship between classroom management (teacher behavioral control, teacher care), motivation to learn and academic performance. The research results indicated that teacher behavioral control and teacher care have positive relationships with motivation to learn and academic performance; motivation to learn is positively related to academic performance. In addition, motivation to learn plays a partial mediator role between classroom management and academic performance. Finally, the study proposed some implications for administrators and teachers in improving classroom management to increase the motivation to learn and the academic performance of students in Business English classes at Ba Ria - Vung Tau University.

KEYWORDS: Academic performance, Classroom management, Motivation to learn.

I. INTRODUCTION

Classroom management is an essential factor in creating motivation and improving learning outcomes for students. Managing a classroom effectively can create a positive learning environment and meet students' learning needs in various ways. Firstly, classroom management can minimize distractions and help students focus on learning. Marzano, Marzano, and Pickering (2003) stated that effective classroom management can significantly reduce disruptions in teaching and learning, increase concentration and achieve better learning outcomes. M.-T. Wang and Holcombe (2010) indicated that a well-managed classroom environment can create active student engagement, enhance their interest and motivation to learn.

Previous studies show that student's academic performance is explained by many factors such as Facebook usage and socialization (Ainin, Naqshbandi, Moghavvemi, & Jaafar, 2015); care and behavioral control in classroom management (Nie & Lau, 2009); teachers' classroom management styles (Djigic & Stojiljkovic, 2011). However, there are limited studies examining the relationship between classroom management and academic performance via the mediating role of motivation to learn of students. The higher the students' motivation, the greater their academic performance (LePine, Lepine, & Jackson, 2004). In addition, the relationship between classroom management and academic performance has not been widely tested.

The Faculty of Foreign Languages – Social Science at BVU provides English language training programs and other training programs. The faculty has a qualified and experienced team of teachers who regularly update their knowledge in their field. However, according to some student evaluations, the Faculty of Foreign Languages – Social Science still faces some issues related to classroom management, student motivation, and academic results. Student learning outcome is often influenced by many factors, such as part-time jobs or individual learning attitudes. In summary, although the Faculty of Foreign Languages – Social Science at BVU has many advantages in terms of faculty and training programs, there is a need to continue improving issues related to classroom management, student motivation, and academic performance to meet the needs of students and the community. In summary, both teacher care and teacher behavioral control have impacts on students' motivation to learn and academic performance. Teachers need to apply appropriate teaching methods and regulations to ensure care and support for students, while also

implementing fair and effective behavioral control. When demonstrated correctly, teacher care and teacher behavioral control can contribute to enhancing students' motivation to learn and academic performance.

Based on the theoretical and practical aspects and in order to address the research gaps above, the author decided to conduct a research to examine the relationship between classroom management, motivation to learn, and academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU.

The study is conducted to test the relationship between classroom management, motivation to learn and academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU. From the test results, the study proposes implications for improving teacher's classroom management to increase the motivation and academic performance of students.

In order to achieve the general objective, the study needs to get the following specific objectives: Identify the measurement components of classroom management in Business English classes at BVU; Determine the relationship between classroom management and academic performance through the mediating role of motivation to learn of students in Business English classes at BVU; Suggest some implications to improve classroom management to increase the motivation and academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH MODEL

2.1. Theoretical framework

This study uses self-determination theory as a theoretical framework to elucidate the impact of a teacher's behavioral control and care on student outcomes. This theory underscores the importance of three fundamental psychological needs - competence, relatedness, and autonomy - in promoting self-motivation and fostering healthy psychological development. This study adopts a self-determination perspective to examine classroom management and highlights several benefits of this approach. Firstly, it resolves empirical and conceptual confusion surrounding the control construct in classroom management literature by clarifying the differences between behavioral control and external control. Furthermore, it provides a reasonable explanation for why behavioral control does not undermine an individual's sense of autonomy, as previously suggested by (Deci, 2008). Secondly, the self-determination theory offers a psychological explanation for the positive effects of teacher care on students' needs satisfaction. Lastly, self-determination theory emphasizes the significance of expanding classroom management's traditional function (i.e., the reduction of misbehavior) to include other crucial indicators of effectiveness, such as engagement and psychological well-being. This theoretical lens allows researchers and teachers to view classroom management from an adaptive motivational and positive psychology perspective.

2.2. Classroom management and its components

Classroom management encompasses the creation of a secure and stimulating learning environment through the teacher's personality, abilities, and professional conduct, which encompasses all of their professional roles, as well as the processes and outcomes that occur within a group of students. Numerous studies have explored the various factors that influence students' academic achievement. M. C. Wang, Haertel, and Walberg (1993) pointed out that, among 228 variables, classroom management has the most direct impact on students' achievements.

Classroom management involves many aspects, including the control of the classroom's layout, activities, materials, and labor as well as the management of students' behavior. This concept is connected to a variety of teacher-led activities in the classroom, including setting up the physical environment, defining and implementing rules, monitoring student behavior, dealing with disruptive behavior, encouraging student ownership of their learning, and designing lessons to help students focus on their tasks (Watkins & Wagner, 2000).

2.2.1. Teacher behavioral control

The definition and operationalization of teacher control involve their efforts to prevent, decrease, and remedy misbehavior while promoting positive behavior. This operationalization pertains to behavioral control rather than external control since it seeks to regulate student behavior through rules and expectations to establish a well-organized environment. Behavioral control is associated with adherence to social norms and expectations. In the educational psychology and self-determination literature, a contextual variable closely related to the concept of behavioral control is structure, which pertains to information about expectations, guidelines, contingencies, or limitations that exist and function within a given social setting (Deci, 2008). The term "behavioral control" is frequently used in classroom management contexts. Deci (2008) claimed that given how they are described in self-

determination theory, behavioral control is more similar to the notion of structure than the concept of external control because both behavioral control and structure are concerned with establishing consistent rules and expectations.

2.2.2. Teacher care

Teachers' care, warmth, support, and involvement are highlighted in the classroom management (Jones & Jones, 2004), developmental (Steinberg, Darling, & Fletcher, 1995) and educational psychology literature (Furrer & Skinner, 2003). The meanings and measures of these concepts often overlap with others. For example, Diamond et al. (2005) defined teacher care as the child's perceived care, warmth, understanding, and affection. Chang (2003) used the term teacher warmth to refer to the qualities of a teacher who cares about, listens to, likes, respects, and understands his/her students. Midgley, Feldlaufer, and Eccles (1989) defined teacher support as students' perceptions of their teachers' care, friendliness, and fairness. Self-determination theorists used the term involvement to refer to teachers' interest in, emotional support for, and affection toward their students (Skinner & Belmont, 1993). From the self-determination perspective, teacher involvement leads to positive student outcomes because it satisfies students' basic needs for relatedness (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

2.2.3. The roles of teacher care and behavioral control in classroom management

In the classroom management literature, there is increasing consensus among researchers that teacher care and behavioral control are not mutually conflicting practices. Hence, it is advisable to blend care and behavioral control in classroom management (Darling-Hammond, Sclan, Sikula, Buttery, & Guyton, 1996). The idea of blending care and behavioral control is based on the assumption that care and behavioral control have specific pathways in relation to different student outcomes, which are vital concerns in classroom management.

2.3. Motivation to learn

Motivation to learn has been defined as the direction, intensity, and persistence of learning-directed behavior and has been found to be positively related to academic performance in a recent meta-analysis (Colquitt, LePine, & Noe, 2000).

The motivation to learn is the power or drive to study, explore, discover and solve problems during the learning process (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Learning motivation is a combination of internal and external factors, including desire, curiosity, confidence, attention, positive feedback, sense of control, and pride in learning (Schunk & Zimmerman, 1997). Learning motivation is defined as the combination of two factors: the value of learning and the hope for success (Pintrich, 2003).

Anderman and Anderman (2020) have pointed out that learning motivation in students can be improved through training programs for teachers and students on how to create a more positive and motivational learning environment. Assor, Kaplan, and Roth (2002) have shown that learning motivation can be improved through education on independence and autonomy for students. Reeve and Jang (2006) have demonstrated that factors such as social support, sense of control, and empathy can affect students' learning motivation.

2.4. Academic performance

Academic performance usually appears in research in education and educational psychology. Two main approaches offer different visions of academic performance. Approaching a specific goal is the most common method to assess academic performance, but avoiding adverse outcomes offers an alternative (Valle, Rodríguez, Cabanach, González-Pienda, & Rosário, 2009). Academic performance is the progress of students or learners in the process of learning, evaluated through tests, assignments, projects, or other quantitative criteria. This definition is widely used in education systems worldwide, where academic performance is assessed and measured by quantitative criteria.

Elliot and Dweck (2005) have defined academic performance as a process of developing the abilities and skills of students or learners, evaluated based on achievements in academic fields or extracurricular activities. In the study of Eccles and Wigfield (2002), academic performance is defined as the attainment of learning goals, including both quantitative and qualitative academic achievements, as well as soft skills developed in the process of learning.

2.5. Research gap

The three research concepts of classroom management, motivation to learn, and academic performance have been extensively studied in previous research. However, previous studies have not clearly established the relationship between classroom management, motivation to learn, and academic performance of students in the context of Business English classes. Therefore, our study aims to fill this gap and provide new insights into the relationship between these factors in the context of Business English

classes at BVU. This study is conducted with the aim of contributing to and filling the research gap that previous studies have not addressed as follows:

Firstly, this study inherits the two components of classroom management, including teacher care and behavioral control, from the study of Nie and Lau (2009). These two components have not been widely tested in relation to motivation to learn and the academic performance of learners.

Secondly, this study contributes by examining the mediating role of motivation to learn through classroom management and academic performance. The role of motivation to learn has yet to be widely tested in previous studies.

Finally, in this study, the author uses the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method to examine the relationships among classroom management, motivation to learn, and academic performance. This data analysis method allows testing with a small sample size and a complex research model.

2.6. Research model and hypotheses

H1: Teacher behavioral control is positively related to academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU.

H2: Teacher care is positively related to academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU.

H3: Teacher behavioral control is positively related to motivation to learn of students in Business English classes at BVU.

H4: Teacher care is positively related to motivation to learn of students in Business English classes at BVU.

H5: Motivation to learn is positively related to academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU.

Classroom Management

Figure 2.1. Proposed research model

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research process

This study was conducted in two main stages: (1) a qualitative study, and (2) a formal quantitative study.

In the preliminary study, based on the research objectives and the synthesis of theoretical basis (background theory, research concepts, and previous studies), the research model, hypotheses, and observed variables with their measurement scales were established. The measurement scales of research concepts at this stage were called draft scale 1. Through group discussions and interviews, the observed variables of the measurement scale were adjusted and supplemented for clarity and suitability to the research context. Based on the collected results, draft scale 1 was developed and adjusted to become draft scale 2 to support quantitative study in the next stage.

In the formal study, the research data was collected through a direct survey method. After the respondents expressed their consent to participate, questionnaires were sent directly to them or through online methods to gather research data for the study. The purpose of this method was to evaluate the appropriateness of the measurement model. The measurement model was evaluated based on the reliability, convergent validity, discriminant validity, and construct validity using Bootstrapping (N = 5000); determination coefficient (R^2), predictive compatibility (Q^2), and effect size (f^2).

3.2. Methods

This study applied a mixed method including qualitative and quantitative methods.

Qualitative method: The author carried out the pilot study via group discussions and interviews with 5 teachers and 10 students. The purpose is to supplement and adjust items of constructs (classroom management, motivation to learn and academic performance) to suit the research context.

Quantitative method: The author conducted an official survey with 203 students who have studied Business English classes at BVU. The purpose is to evaluate the model and test the research hypotheses.

3.3. Data

The data in this study was collected through group discussions, interviews and a survey questionnaire.

- For the group discussions and interviews conducted in the pilot study:

Group discussions and interviews with teachers and students: The study conducted group discussions and interviews with teachers and students to improve items measuring the constructs of classroom management, motivation to learn and academic performance. These constructs are inherited from previous studies, so they need to be adjusted and supplemented to fit the research context at BVU.

- For the survey questionnaire method used in the official study:

After completing the constructs, a questionnaire was developed in the final analysis. The questionnaire was sent to students to collect information directly or via online channels. The study uses 5-levels Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree.

3.4. Analysis of the data

After data collection stage, the data was entered into SPSS 25 software. The data was cleaned and processed in the following steps:

Step 1: Constructs in the theoretical model were tested for reliability through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. If Cronbach's Alpha coefficient > 0.6 and total variable correlation coefficient > 0.3 , the constructs meet the requirements of reliability.

Step 2: Constructs were evaluated by composite reliability, and the average variance extracted from constructs was evaluated. The composite reliability of the scales must be greater than 0.6 and average variance extracted must be greater than 0.5 in order to meet the allowable requirements.

Step 3: To test the proposed hypotheses, the study applied Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Characteristics of the sample

Table 4.1. Characteristics of the study sample

		Frequency	%
Gender	Female	65	32.0%
	Male	138	68.0%
Student	First-year student	51	25.1%
	Second-year student	31	15.3%
	Third-year student	37	18.2%
	Four-year student	84	41.4%

The data in Table 4.1 pertains to the gender and academic year distribution among the study sample. Of the 203 students, 32.0% are female, while 68.0% are male. Regarding academic year, 25.1% are first-year students, 15.3% are second-year students, 18.2% are third-year students, and 41.4% are fourth-year students.

4.2. Testing the reliability of the components in the research model

The results of the internal consistency and convergent validity analyses suggest that all four constructs (AP, MTL, TBC, and TC) have good psychometric properties. The values for Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and AVE are all above the commonly accepted thresholds of 0.70, 0.80, and 0.50, respectively. Therefore, these constructs are likely to be reliable and valid measures of the underlying constructs they are intended to measure.

The results of the outer loadings analysis suggest that the items used to measure the constructs of AP, MTL, TBC, and TC are reliable and valid measures of their corresponding constructs. This provides support for the use of these items in future research studies or practical applications.

The results of the Fornell-Larcker criterion analysis suggest that each construct (AP, MTL, TBC, and TC) has discriminant validity from the other constructs. This supports the use of these constructs in future research studies or practical applications.

4.3. Testing the research hypotheses

4.3.1. Direct effect testing

The results of testing the relationships between the components in the research model are presented in Figure 4.1. The estimation method used is the Bootstrapping technique with N = 5000 observations in PLS-SEM.

Figure 4.1. PLS-SEM results

Table 4.2. Path coefficients

Hypotheses	Path coefficients	Original sample (O)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values	Conclusion
H1	TBC → AP	0.177**	0.074	2.41	0.016	Accepted
H2	TBC → MTL	0.152**	0.064	2.372	0.018	Accepted
H3	TC → AP	0.151*	0.077	1.956	0.051	Accepted
H4	TC → MTL	0.157**	0.062	2.514	0.012	Accepted
H5	MTL → AP	0.411***	0.056	7.395	0.000	Accepted

Note: p < 0.01, 0.5, 0.1 corresponds to ***, **, and ***

The table above reports the results of a t-test analysis that examines the statistical significance of the relationships between pairs of constructs. The t-test is used to determine whether the difference between the means of two samples is statistically significant. In this case, the original sample (O) represents the correlation coefficient between two constructs, and the sample mean (M), standard deviation, T statistics, and p-values are reported.

From Table 4.5, it can be seen that all of the t statistics are greater than 1.96, which corresponds to a significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the relationships between all pairs of constructs are statistically significant at the 0.05, 0.1 level.

The T statistic for the relationship between MTL and AP is 7.395, which is much larger than 1.96. This suggests that the relationship between MTL and AP is statistically significant, so H1 is accepted.

The p-values in the table also provide information about the statistical significance of the relationships between the pairs of constructs. All p-values which indicates that the relationships between all pairs of constructs are statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

The results show that TBC has a positive effect on AP, and this effect is statistically significant ($B = 0.177, p = 0.016 < 0.05$), thus supporting hypothesis H1. Similarly, hypothesis H2 is also supported as TBC has a positive effect on MTL, and this effect is statistically significant ($B = 0.152, p = 0.018 < 0.05$). Furthermore, TC also has a positive and statistically significant effect on AP ($B = 0.151, p = 0.051 < 0.1$), thus supporting hypothesis H3. Likewise, hypothesis H4 is supported as TC has a positive and statistically significant effect on MTL ($B = 0.157, p = 0.012 < 0.05$). Finally, MTL has a positive and statistically significant effect on AP ($B = 0.411, p = 0.000$), thus supporting hypothesis H5.

Overall, the results of the t-test analysis suggest that there are statistically significant relationships between pairs of constructs. These results provide support for the use of these constructs in future research studies or practical applications.

4.3.2. Indirect effect testing

Table 4.3. Indirect path coefficients

Indirect effect	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	Confidence intervals (CIs)		P values
			2.50%	97.50%	
TBC -> MTL -> AP	0.062	2.316	0.012	0.119	0.021
TC -> MTL -> AP	0.065	2.34	0.015	0.124	0.019

Table 4.6 shows the results of testing the indirect effects of TBC and TC on AP through MTL. The indirect effect of TBC on AP through MTL is estimated to be 0.062, with a T statistic of 2.316, indicating that the effect is statistically significant (p-value of 0.021). The 2.50% and 97.50% confidence intervals for this indirect effect are 0.012 and 0.119, respectively. The estimated coefficient of 0.062 falls within the confidence interval and does not contain the value of 0, indicating that MTL partially mediates the relationship between TBC and AP.

Similarly, the indirect effect of TC on AP through MTL is estimated to be 0.065, with a T statistic of 2.34, indicating that the effect is statistically significant (p-value of 0.019). The 2.50% and 97.50% confidence intervals for this indirect effect are 0.015 and 0.124, respectively, and do not contain the value of 0. The estimated coefficient of $B = 0.065$ falls within this confidence interval, indicating that MTL partially mediates the relationship between TC and AP.

4.4. Discussions

The results indicated that two components of classroom management (teacher behavioral control and teacher care) are positively related to academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU. The results of this study are consistent with previous research. [Adedigba and Sulaiman \(2020\)](#) showed that teachers' classroom management style influenced academic achievement in Kwara State. [Ahmad, Hussain Ch, Ayub, Zaheer, and Batool \(2017\)](#) demonstrated that classroom management strategies are positively related to the academic performance of students at college level. [Omodan, Ekundayo, and Ige \(2018\)](#) supported enhancing students' academic performance in secondary schools via classroom management skills. The relationship between classroom management and academic performance has been widely tested in previous studies. In this study, the author

drew on the self-determination theory perspective and tested the extent to which the components of classroom management, such as teacher behavioral control and teacher care, are related to academic performance in Business English classes.

Furthermore, the study results indicated that teacher behavioral control and teacher care are positively related to the motivation to learn of students in Business English classes at BVU. These findings are consistent with previous research. [Tran Thi Thuong and Nguyen Thi Hong Thu \(2021\)](#) showed that classroom management styles influence students' motivation in learning English. [Adedigba and Sulaiman \(2020\)](#) proposed the influence of teachers' classroom management style on pupils' motivation for learning in Kwara State.

Finally, the study found that motivation to learn is positively related to the academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU. These results are consistent with previous research, such as [Wu, Li, Zheng, and Guo \(2020\)](#), showing that there is a positive relation between motivation and academic performance of medical students in KUCs.

V. CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

This study analyzed the relationship between teacher behavioral control, teacher care, motivation to learn, and academic performance using the PLS-SEM method and bootstrapping technique with $N = 5000$ observations. The results showed that both teacher behavioral control and teacher care have positive effects on academic performance through the mediating effect of motivation to learn. Specifically, motivation to learn is identified as an important mediating factor between teacher behavioral control/ teacher care and academic performance. These findings provided further insights into the role of motivation to learn in the process of transmitting the effects of teacher behavioral control/ teacher care on academic performance.

This study provided valuable information to enhance understanding of the relationship between factors influencing the development of academic performance while also providing a basis for proposing measures to improve academic performance.

For objective 1, the study identified the measurement components of classroom management in Business English classes at BVU as teacher behavioral control and teacher care. These two factors are suitable for the research context at BVU for students in Business English classes.

For objective 2, the study determined the relationship between classroom management and academic performance through the mediating role of motivation to learn among students in Business English classes at BVU. Specifically, teacher behavioral control and teacher care have positive and direct impacts on academic performance, and also have positive and indirect impacts on academic performance through the partially mediating role of motivation to learn.

For objective 3, some implications for the administrators and teachers to improve classroom management in order to increase motivation and academic performance of students in Business English classes at BVU were proposed and presented in section 5.2.

5.2. Managerial implications

In teacher behavioral control, the mean score of 3.62 for "teacher corrects misbehavior immediately" suggests timely intervention by teachers. However, a standard deviation of 1.06 indicates varied student perceptions. To enhance this, administrators and teachers should establish consistent behavior expectations, develop timely response systems, and offer teacher training in classroom management. The mean score of 3.6355 for "teacher tells the class to keep quiet when noisy" reflects teacher efforts in managing noise levels. A lower standard deviation of 0.94141 indicates more uniform perceptions. To further improve, teachers can reinforce quiet environments, facilitate focus-building activities, and apply consistent consequences for noise disruptions. The item "teacher takes note of misbehaviors" has a mean of 3.5320 and a standard deviation of 0.99638. Students feel teacher's record inappropriate behaviors, but variations exist. Recommendations include robust behavior management systems, teacher training, student feedback mechanisms, enhanced parent communication, and continuous evaluation. For "teacher takes action to ensure good behavior," the mean is 3.4828, with a standard deviation of 0.92461. Students perceive teachers' efforts to promote positive behavior, though perceptions vary. To enhance this, teachers should establish clear behavior rules, implement effective classroom management techniques, provide opportunities for good behavior display, improve parent communication, and conduct regular evaluations. In summary, the study underscores the significance of teacher behavioral control. Administrators and teachers should focus on consistent behavior expectations, timely responses, noise management, recording misbehavior, and ensuring good behavior through effective techniques.

In teacher care, item Teacher Concern for Students with a mean score of 3.8916 and low standard deviation shows that students perceive teacher concern positively. To enhance this, teachers are advised to establish personal connections, provide consistent feedback and support, create a supportive environment, respond compassionately to concerns, and model empathy. For item Warm and Friendly Classroom Environment, the mean score of 3.6749 indicates a positive perception of a welcoming environment. Teachers can further enhance this by greeting students warmly, using humor and positive reinforcement, encouraging collaborative work, demonstrating respect and inclusivity, and fostering a sense of community. In item Acceptance of Different Opinions, the mean score of 3.3645 suggests room for improvement in accepting diverse opinions. Teachers can encourage open discussions, create a safe space for opinions, respond respectfully, provide varied channels for expression, and value diverse perspectives. In item Openness to Student Suggestions, the mean score of 3.6207 reflects students' perception of teacher openness, with some variability. Teachers can improve by encouraging idea-sharing, active listening, constructive responses, integration of suggestions, and involving students in decision-making. In conclusion, teacher care is crucial for effective classroom dynamics. Teachers can enhance student experiences by fostering personal connections, creating welcoming environments, valuing diverse opinions, and being open to suggestions. These findings provide valuable insights for promoting a positive and supportive learning atmosphere.

In motivation to learn, item "In general, I exert considerable effort to learning the material in my courses" has a mean score of 3.5369 and moderate standard deviation. Students generally perceive putting considerable effort into learning. To further support this, teachers can set clear objectives, employ varied teaching methods, offer feedback, create a positive environment, and encourage student ownership of their learning process. For item "In general, I try to learn as much as I can from my courses", the mean score of 3.4778 reflects students' intent to maximize learning, with a relatively high standard deviation. Teachers are advised to promote goal-setting, use diverse teaching approaches, provide feedback, foster a positive environment, and engage students in meaningful interactions with course material. For item "In general, I am motivated to learn the skills emphasized in my courses", the mean score of 3.5320 indicates motivation to learn emphasized skills, with moderate variability. Teachers can enhance motivation by emphasizing skills' real-world relevance, adapting teaching strategies, offering positive reinforcement, incorporating practical examples, and encouraging skill application.

In conclusion, the research findings concluded that teacher behavioral control and care are two essential teacher behaviors that can influence students' motivation to learn and academic performance in Business English classes at BVU. Teacher behavioral control refers to the extent to which a teacher uses specific behaviors to regulate student behavior. In contrast, teacher care refers to the extent to which a teacher shows concern and support for students' well-being. Studies have shown that teacher behavioral control and teacher care are positively related to students' learning motivation. Motivation to learn is a psychological construct reflecting students' drive and willingness to engage in learning activities. Students more motivated to learn are more likely to engage in learning activities, which can lead to better academic performance. To improve the academic performance of Business English students at BVU, the study suggested that teachers can focus on improving their behavioral control and care in the classroom, leading to higher motivation to learn among students. Teachers can use specific strategies, such as providing clear expectations and rules for behavior and showing genuine interest and concern for their students, to enhance their behavioral control and care. Teachers can also provide opportunities for students to participate in activities that are interesting and relevant to their lives, which can further increase their motivation to learn.

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